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MATERIAL SIMULATION SETTINGS FOR MICROSTRUCTURAL MODELLING

enable

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CCT- Continuous Cooling Transformation
CDRX- Continuous Dynamic Recrystallisation
CNGT- Classical Nucleation and Growth Theory
DDRX- Discontinuous Dynamic Recrystallisation
DRV- Dynamic Recovery
DRX- Dynamic Recrystallisation
DSC- Differential Scanning Calorimetry
EBSD- Electron Back-Scattered Diffraction
ECAP- Equal-Channel Angular Pressing
FSW- Friction Stir Welding
GBS- Grain Boundary Sliding
GDRX- Geometrical Dynamic Recrystallisation
GP- Guinier-Preston
HAGB- High Angle Grain Boundary
HPS- High Pressure Sliding
HPT- High Pressure Torsion
LAGB- Low Angle Grain Boundary
MDRX- Meta-Dynamic Recrystallisation
PDRX- Post-Dynamic Recrystallisation
PSN- Particle Stimulated Nucleation
RX- Recrystallisation
SEM- Scanning Electron Microscope
SHPB- Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar
SHT- Solution Heat Treatment
SPD- Severe Plastic Deformation
SSSS- Super Saturated Solid Solution
TMP- Thermo-Mechanical Processing
TTT- Time-Temperature Transformation
UFG- Ultrafine Grain

1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of the current research work is to develop physical model for three aerospace materials (Ti64, IN718 and AA7075-T6) based on their microstructural changes taking place during the plastic deformation; such as dynamic recrystallisation (DRX), grain growth, dislocation density evolution, precipitation dissolution etc. Such models can simulate the mechanical and microstructural behaviour of the materials over the entire range of temperature (from room to semi-solid) and strain rate (from quasi-static to very high). In other words, the mechanical response of the materials can be predicted for any given temperature and strain rate by considering the dominant physical mechanism behind the plastic deformation. During the manufacturing processes such as cutting, machining, milling, turning, high rate forging, shot peening, shock welding, laser surface processing and Friction Stir Welding (FSW), materials experience deformation at high temperature and high strain rate. The proposed model can not only be used for anticipating the state of the material at the end of the manufacturing chain but also be employed for large-scale finite element simulations of many complicated engineering systems and processes including automotive crashworthiness, aerospace impacts due to bird and space debris ingestion in jet engines, defence applications etc.

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a list of parameters which are to be used in modelling different microstructural phenomena mentioned above. The values of these parameters could be obtained from the literature (properties of the material), mechanical characterisation (flow stress behaviour), microstructural analysis (of specimens after plastic deformation) and model calibration (results from experiments and simulations). In order to study the mechanical response of the selected materials, various experiments were scheduled to be performed at different loading conditions as listed in Table 1.1.

This deliverable basically consists of two segments. The first section discusses about the microstructural background of the selected materials in terms of precipitation evolution, phase transformation and DRX. The second section is focused on the basic structure and the underlying physical mechanisms of several microstructural models already implemented by other researchers. The physical model to be developed in this research work could use the simulation settings advocated by these pre-existing models complemented with additional information from the literature and microstructural analysis of the specimens deformed during the mechanical tests. Part of this deliverable has been reproduced and extended from Deliverable 1.1 and 1.2.

		Strain (ϵ)		
		Low (< 1)	High (> 1)	
IN718 (solution heat-treated and aged)	Strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$	Low ($\leq 1 s^{-1}$)	Compression tests with Gleeble ⁽¹⁾ (for 20°C to 1100°C)	Torsion tests with Gleeble ⁽¹⁾
		High ($\geq 100 s^{-1}$)	Compression test with SHPB ⁽²⁾ (for 20°C to 1100°C)	Torsion tests with Flywheel device ⁽³⁾
Ti-6Al-4V		Low ($\leq 1 s^{-1}$)	Compression tests with Gleeble ⁽¹⁾ (for 20 to 1100°C)	Torsion tests (for 1000°C to 1100°C)
		High ($\geq 100 s^{-1}$)	Compression tests with SHPB ⁽²⁾ (for 20 to 950°C)	Torsion tests with Flywheel device ⁽³⁾
AA7075-T6		Low ($\leq 5 s^{-1}$)	Compression tests with Gleeble ⁽¹⁾ (for 20 to 550°C)	Torsion tests with Gleeble ⁽¹⁾
		High ($\geq 100 s^{-1}$)	Compression tests with SHPB ⁽²⁾ (for 20 to 550°C)	Torsion tests with Flywheel device ⁽³⁾

⁽¹⁾ Gleeble: Gleeble thermo-mechanical simulator
⁽²⁾ SHPB: Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar (+ induction heating) – strain rate between 1000 s⁻¹ and 5000 s⁻¹
⁽³⁾ Flywheel device with a torsion module developed by ESR3 – strain rate between 100 s⁻¹ and 1000 s⁻¹

Table 1.1: Experiments planned in this project according to the loading conditions

2 MICROSTRUCTURE OF SELECTED MATERIALS

The deformation behaviour of a material depends on its initial microstructure and the loading conditions (temperature, strain and strain rate), and it controls the final microstructure and properties of the material. Therefore, in order to accurately model the evolution of the microstructure and mechanical properties in a material, its deformation mechanisms have to be studied and understood.

In this section, the major mechanisms governing plastic deformation of the three materials of interest, Ti64, IN718 and AA7075-T6, are detailed. Those are phase transformation, precipitation evolution and recrystallisation.

2.1 Ti-6Al-4V (Ti64)

Titanium alloys are known for their high specific strength and excellent corrosion resistance. Ti-6Al-4V, developed in the 1950s, was the very first titanium alloy to be made and it represents nowadays 50% of the titanium alloys usage [1]. This alloy presents excellent strength to density ratio, as well as excellent corrosion and fatigue resistance. It is used mainly in the aerospace industry, which the first consumer of titanium alloys. However, its usage has extended to other sectors of activity, such as chemistry, and, due to its biocompatibility, it can also be found in surgical implants and sport equipment.

2.1.1 Phase transformation in Ti-6Al-4V

Ti-6Al-4V is a two-phase alloy, classified among the $\alpha + \beta$ titanium alloys. It owes its good balance of properties to the addition of Aluminium (Al) and Vanadium (V). The two phases of Ti-6Al-4V are presented in Table 2.1.

<i>Phase</i>	<i>Crystal Structure</i>	<i>Temperature range in pure Titanium</i>	<i>Stabilizer in Ti-6Al-4V</i>	<i>Temperature range in Ti-6Al-4V</i>
α	HPC	$T < T_{\beta}(\text{Ti}) = 883^{\circ}\text{C}$	Al	$T < T_{\beta}(\text{Ti64}) = 995^{\circ}\text{C}$
β	BCC	$T_{\beta}(\text{Ti}) = 883^{\circ}\text{C} < T < T_{\text{fusion}}$	V	$T < T_{\text{fusion}}$

Table 2.1: Properties of the different phases in Ti-6Al-4V

The β -phase is more ductile and has better formability than the α -phase, but lower strength. 883°C corresponds to the β -transus temperature of pure titanium $T_{\beta}(\text{Ti})$, which is define as the temperature at which the α -phase changes into β -phase. Due to the addition of alloying elements, the β -transus temperature of Ti-6Al-4V, $T_{\beta}(\text{Ti64})$, is equal to 995°C and it corresponds to the transition from a two-phase field $\alpha + \beta$ to a single β -phase. At room temperature, the alloy is composed of nearly 95% of α -phase and 5% of retained β -phase.

The microstructure of Ti-6Al-4V depends on the heat-treatment, as different types of α and β phases can be formed. A continuous cooling transformation (CCT) diagram as presented in Figure 2.1, can be used to predict the final microstructure of the material.

Figure 2.1: CCT diagram of Ti-6Al-4V [125]

Ti-6Al-4V can exhibit different types of microstructures, classified among lamellar and equiaxed. Lamellar microstructures are composed of α lamellas in a β -phase matrix. Equiaxed microstructures are characterized by globular α grains in a β -phase matrix. The material is qualified as bi-modal, or duplex, when its microstructure is in between lamellar and equiaxed. Ti-6Al-4V is extremely sensitive to the heat-treatment temperatures and cooling rates, as it shown on Figure 2.2.

Different heat-treatment procedures and their resulting microstructures and mechanical properties are presented in Table 2.2. Figure 2.3 shows optical micrographs of the microstructures.

Figure 2.2: Effect of heating temperatures and cooling rates on microstructures of TIMETAL 6-4 [126]

Heat treatment	Procedure	Resulting microstructure	Properties
None	-	Fine equiaxed	UTS = 1163 MPa HV = 340 Mean grain size: 6.5 μm
β annealing	1050° C during 30 min + slow cooling to RT	Coarse lamellar	UTS = 1090 MPa HV = 290 Mean grain size: 735 μm Laths thickness: 6.8 μm
β annealing	1050° C during 30 min + air cooling to RT	Fine lamellar	UTS = 1123 MPa HV = 330 Mean grain size: 573 μm Laths thickness: 0.7 μm
$\alpha + \beta$ annealing	15 min at 930° C plus air cooling to RT + 120 min at 630° C + air cooling to RT	Bi-modal	UTS = 1115 MPa HV = 313 Mean grain size: 6.5 μm

Table 2.2: Microstructure and properties of Ti-6Al-4V depending on the heat-treatment [2]

Figure 2.3: Optical micrographs of different microstructures obtained by heat treatments (a) initial material, (b) coarse lamellar, (c) fine lamellar, (d) bi-modal (duplex) [2]

The microstructure of the initial (without heat treatment) material, Figure 2.3 (a), comes from a relatively complex thermo-mechanical treatment in the $\alpha+\beta$ two-phase domain of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy. This treatment is used to break some of the α_p (primary α phase) laths already formed. The α_p is formed during the solution heat-treatment in the $\alpha+\beta$ domain. During the rolling of the sheets, the debris of α_p can coalesce and recrystallize into small nodules which grow to obtain nodular primary α grains (α_{pn}). The size of these grains depends on the temperature and the duration of the heat treatment. These nodules can only be completely re-dissolved if the material is heated above the β -transus temperature (995° C). The phases β_m and β_s are trapped outside the nodules to form a β -matrix. The metastable β_m phase corresponds to the non-equilibrium primary β -phase, capable of being transformed and which can be retained at ambient temperature by a local chemical composition which remains close to that of high temperatures. The stable β_s phase at room temperature is the primary β -phase retained at ambient temperature and stable due to a local concentration of β -stabiliser sufficient to maintain it, e.g. 15% of vanadium [2].

2.1.2 Dynamic recrystallisation in Ti-6Al-4V

Under the β -transus temperature, Ti-6Al-4V has two phases, α and β . During hot deformation ($650^\circ\text{C} < T < 995^\circ\text{C}$), softening can be caused by two mechanisms: Globularisation and/or dynamic recrystallisation (DRX).

Globularisation or dynamic spheroidization have been observed in the α -phase of Ti-6Al-4V alloy [3] [4]. Globularisation is defined as a static and dynamic coarsening when grains not only grow but also become more globular [5]. It can also correspond to an evolution from a lamellar α -phase to a globular α -phase, as illustrated in Figure 2.5 [3]. As the grain boundaries move through the lattice and annihilate the dislocations, the dislocation density decreases and so does the flow stress. Other researchers have observed DRX under the β -transus temperature in Ti-6Al-4V [6] [7]. The main softening mechanisms were identified to be dynamic recovery (DRV) and Continuous Dynamic Recrystallisation (CDRX), as it usually is in high stacking fault materials. Chen and Coyne [8] have observed both globular and recrystallized α grains. However, Majorell et al. [9] observed neither grain growth nor recrystallisation.

Figure 2.5: Schematic drawing of Globularisation of lamellar α -phase in Ti-6Al-4V [3]

S. Bruschi et al. [10] studied relatively large strain deformation (until 0.9) of Ti-6Al-4V alloy by means of hot compression tests at $880 - 950^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range and $1 - 50\text{ s}^{-1}$ strain rate range. He found out that at high temperature, work hardening occurs only when the deformation is quite small (approximately for strains less than 10%). But increasing the deformation, the work softening becomes dominant. At temperatures above 950°C , at low strain rate, both the peak flow stress and the steady-state flow are shifted to lower stress levels due to the formation of β -phase.

Above the β -transus temperature, all the α -phase is dissolved and Ti-6Al-4V becomes a single β -phase alloy. In this case, DRV and CDRX of the β -phase was identified as the main mechanism controlling the evolution of the microstructure [11] [12]. A grain fragmentation occurs by the generation of new grain boundaries. This mechanism generates reduced and equiaxed grains that could be much smaller than the initial one. R. Ding et al. [37] investigated dynamic

and/or meta-dynamic recrystallisation (MDRX) when the Ti-6Al-4V alloy was processed in the β -phase field. The author obtained a similar recrystallised grain with embedded martensitic phase and the recrystallised grain size stabilises itself around 13-14 μm , regardless to the initial heat treatment or process parameters. This suggests that the CDRX mechanism predominates with respect to β -grain growth. It is known that β -grain growth is rapid in the β -phase field because of high temperature and absence of second-phase particle to impede grain boundary motion, but this phenomenon is totally occluded in by the recrystallisation phenomenon.

During high strain rate deformation, limited softening has been observed, indicating DRV or thermal softening due to adiabatic heating, but no recrystallisation [5] [13] [14]. Furthermore, Ti-6Al-4V is prone to strain localization and adiabatic shear failure, especially at high strain rate [5] [13].

Large deformation of the metals is studied by using many experimental tests like hot torsion test [11], severe plastic deformation (SPD) [15], high-pressure sliding (HPS) [16], etc. at very high temperature. But there is no information available on the large deformation ($\epsilon > 1$) of Ti-6Al-4V alloy at low temperature ($T < 400^\circ\text{C}$). Ti-6Al-4V being a high strength material, if the temperature of the material is not high enough then it ruptures before it reaches the strain level of $\epsilon > 1$. If the test is performed at a high strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon} > 10^3\text{ s}^{-1}$), then there is not much evidence on large deformation, also the time required to obtain the DRX will not be enough and there is the possibility to observe adiabatic shear bands. So, there is no specific value of the high strain rate explained in any literature to obtain the DRX.

Table 2.3 presents a summary of the different deformation mechanisms observed in Ti-6Al-4V depending on the loading conditions.

		$T < 400^\circ\text{C}$	$400^\circ\text{C} < T < 995^\circ\text{C}$	$T > 995^\circ\text{C}$
<i>Low strain (<1)</i>	<i>Low strain rate (< 10 s⁻¹)</i>	Hardening behaviour dominant [5]	Softening due to Globularisation and/or DRX (CRDX + DRV) [5] [7] [4] [3]	Hardening behaviour dominant [7] [4]
	<i>High strain rate (> 1000 s⁻¹)</i>	Hardening behaviour dominant [5] [13]	Hardening behaviour dominant [5] [13]	Hardening behaviour dominant [13]
<i>Large strain (>1)</i>	<i>Low strain rate (< 10 s⁻¹)</i>	Hardening and failure before reaching large strains		Softening due to DRX (CRDX + DRV) [11]
	<i>High strain rate (> 1000 s⁻¹)</i>			<i>Actual tests cannot meet those conditions</i>

Table 2.3: Deformation behaviour of Ti-6Al-4V depending on the loading conditions

2.2 Alloy 718

Alloy 718 is a nickel-based superalloy. It was developed in the 1960s and it is nowadays one of the most widely used superalloy due to its high strength, high corrosion resistance and good mechanical properties at high temperature. It presents also good fatigue, creep and wear resistance. It is mainly used in the aerospace industry, in the hot parts of gas turbine engines.

2.2.1 Phase transformation and precipitation evolution in alloy 718

Alloy 718 is a precipitate hardening alloy classified among the γ - γ' - γ'' nickel-based superalloys. Thus, it is composed of a Ni-Cr matrix, the γ phase, and two main precipitates, γ' and γ'' , as well as δ -phase precipitates. The characteristics of the different phases in alloy 718 are presented in Table 2.4.

Phase	γ	γ'	γ''	δ
Composition	Ni(Fe,Cr)	Ni ₃ Al(Ti, Nb)	Ni ₃ Nb(Ti, Al)	Ni ₃ Nb(Ti, Al)
Crystal structure	FCC	FCC (L ₁₂)	BCT (D ₀₂₂)	Orthorhombic (D _{0_a})
Lattice parameter	$a_{(Ni)} = 3.52 \text{ \AA}$	$a_{(Ni_3Al)} = 3.57 \text{ \AA}$	$a_{(Ni_3Nb)} = 3.62 \text{ \AA}$ $c_{(Ni_3Nb)} = 7.4 \text{ \AA}$	$a_{(\delta)} = 5.11 \text{ \AA}$ $b_{(\delta)} = 4.24 \text{ \AA}$ $c_{(\delta)} = 4.54 \text{ \AA}$
Relation with the matrix	-	Coherent	Semi-coherent	Incoherent
Particle morphology	-	Spherical << 1 μm	Disc $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$	Extensive thin plates up to 20 μm long ~ 1 μm of thickness
Precipitation temperature range	-	650°C to 850°C	620°C to 900°C	750°C to 1000°C (depending on the Nb content)
<p><i>Chemical elements indicated in brackets means they substitute randomly the element before the brackets. For example, in the matrix, Ni atoms are randomly substituted by Fe or Cr atoms.</i></p> <p><i>L₁₂, D₀₂₂ and D_{0_a} correspond to the Strukturbericht notation [17] [18]</i></p>				

Table 2.4: Characteristics of the different phases in alloy 718 [19] [20]

Figure 2.6: Strukturbericht (a) L12 γ' -phase (b) D022 γ'' -phase (c) D0a δ -phase Ni atoms are in orange on (a) and (c) and in pink on (b). Al atoms are in yellow. Nb atoms are in grey.

Although alloy 718 is considered as a γ - γ' - γ'' Ni-alloy, it is thought that γ' precipitates have only a minor effect on the material properties and that most of the hardening effect comes from the γ'' precipitates [21] [22].

Two nucleation mechanisms for δ precipitates have been identified, intergranular and intragranular [23]. The first one refers to the formation of δ -phase at the grain boundaries during heat-treatment up to 1000°C [19]. The second mechanism is the transformation of γ'' precipitates, which are metastable, into δ precipitates when reaching a critical size, above which the structure is not stable anymore [24] [20]. This transformation occurs at relatively high temperature, when growth of precipitates is promoted. Precipitation of δ phase is thought to occur mainly through transformation of γ'' precipitates up to 900°C, after which γ'' precipitates are dissolved.

The presence of δ precipitates at the grain boundaries allows to control the grain size by limiting grain coarsening [25]. However, the transformation of γ'' precipitates into δ phase usually induces a decrease in strength, as the δ precipitates replace the hardening γ'' precipitates, so it is considered as undesirable [23]. This transformation can occur from around 650°C [24], which is thus set to be the upper temperature limit for the operational conditions of alloy 718 [24] [25].

The size of the precipitates can be controlled by heat treatment [19] [26]. Two time-temperature-transformation (TTT) diagrams of alloy 718 are presented in Figure 2.7 [27] [23]. It has been observed that precipitation and dissolution mechanisms can be different depending on the initial material [23]. It can be noted that around 1000°C, depending on the Nb content [19], all the precipitates are dissolved, and the alloy becomes a single-phase material with additional elements in solid solution [28].

Figure 2.7: TTT diagrams of alloy 718 reported by [27], [23], respectively.

In this project, two types of alloy 718 are studied: solution heat-treated and aged. The corresponding thermal treatments are presented in Figure 2.8. Using the TTT diagram as shown in Figure 2.7, it is expected that the aging treatment leads to precipitation of γ'' precipitates.

Figure 2.8: Heat-treatment for alloy 718 samples

Predominant carbides in alloy 718 were identified to be primary NbC carbides, with an irregular and blocky morphology. In the solution heat-treated state, carbides are distributed both inside the grains and at grain boundaries [29] [30]. During aging between 700° C and 900° C, they nucleate exclusively at the grain boundaries after long aging time (~ 100h) [29].

2.2.2 Dynamic recrystallisation in IN718

The hot deformation behaviour of alloy 718 is significantly affected by the processing parameter and initial microstructure.

During compression at low to high temperature (until around 900° C), deformation behaviour is dominated by strain hardening [31]. However, it is expected that recovery mechanisms take place, simultaneously with strain hardening. Lee et al. [32] [33] observed that increasing the strain rate and decreasing the temperature result in a rise in flow stress, yield strength, strain rate sensitivity and temperature sensitivity.

The deformation behaviour at very high temperature (above 900° C) is dominated by DRX. Being a relatively low stacking fault material, discontinuous dynamic recrystallisation (DDRX) is expected to be the main restoration process. However, depending on the deformation temperature and strain rate, CDRX can also occur [34] [28] [35]. M. Azarbarmas et al. [36] have investigated the occurrence of DDRX and CDRX in alloy 718 at low strain rate (up to 1 s⁻¹) and they found that CDRX is promoted at higher strain, higher strain rate and lower

temperature. However, DDRX stays the dominant deformation mechanism, especially at low strain [36] [35]. F. Montheillet et al. [34] have observed that the DDRX kinetic in this alloy is relatively low and that its nucleation occurs through three mechanisms: twinning, "continuous nucleation" (generation of high angle grain boundaries (HAGB) by the progressive misorientation of subgrain, leading to the formation of nuclei) and nucleation by bulging. Twinning has been proven to accelerate the DRX process, as twins decrease the boundary energy of growing grains, thus being a preferred site for nucleation [34] [36] [37].

DRX has not been reported in the case of high strain rate deformation, except under shear loading. Alloy 718 having a high strength at elevated temperature, it is susceptible to form adiabatic shear bands during machining, which requires very high strain rate and temperature [38]. In this case, DRX occurs in the adiabatic shear bands [39]. In addition, X. Wang et al. [40] have investigated the behaviour of alloy 718 at very high strain rate ($> 5000 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and they found that strain rate softening can occur. In this case, the dislocation density is high enough to produce annihilation of the dislocation and the temperature rises, so the movement of dislocations is easier, leading to a softening effect. The effect of strain rate, hardening or softening, depends on the temperature.

Large deformation of IN718 is only possible at high temperature ($T > 900^\circ \text{C}$) and low strain rate ($< 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Below this temperature material undergoes fracture before it reaches the strain value of $\epsilon > 1$, due to its high strength. Y. Takizawa [16] studied the superplastic deformation of IN718 at a very low strain rate ($< 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) at high temperatures. They found that the deformation is mainly controlled by grain boundary sliding with the activation energy for lattice diffusion, while the recrystallisation, grain growth and twin formation can be major processes facilitating the grain boundary sliding.

Table 2.5 presents a summary of the deformation behaviour in alloy 718 depending on the temperature, strain and strain rate.

		$T < 900^\circ \text{C}$	$T > 900^\circ \text{C}$
Low strain (< 1)	Low strain rate ($< 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Hardening behaviour dominant [31]	Softening due to DDRX and CDRX [36] [41] [8] [28] [42] [43] [44] [45] [37] [35] [46]
	High strain rate ($> 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Hardening behaviour weakened by thermal softening [33] [40]	Hardening behaviour weakened by thermal softening [40]
		$T < 800^\circ \text{C}$	$T > 800^\circ \text{C}$
Large strain (> 1)	Low strain rate ($< 10 \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Hardening and failure before reaching large strains	Softening due to DDRX and CDRX [47]
	High strain rate ($> 1000 \text{ s}^{-1}$)		Actual tests cannot meet those conditions

Table 2.5: Deformation behaviour of alloy 718 depending on the loading conditions 19

2.3 Aluminium alloy 7075 tempered at T6 (AA7075-T6)

AA7075 alloy belongs to the Al-Zn-Mg-Cu series with Zn constituting the highest of 5-6 % of the total weight. On account of the high mechanical strength, light weight, dimensional stability, machinability, good vibration-damping characteristics and stiffness in its T6 tempered condition [48], AA7075 is widely used in the structural applications in aerospace, military and automobile industries, such as in aircraft fittings, fuse parts, shafts and gears, missile parts, regulating valves, worm gears, sensor and guidance components for flight and satellite systems etc. [49]. AA7075-T6 exhibits the best combination of strength and fracture toughness compared to other Al alloys. Though, it lacks weldability and corrosion resistance.

2.3.1 Precipitation evolution in AA7075-T6 alloy

Normally the heat treatment process for T6 temper of extruded AA7075 alloy consists of the following two steps [49] [50] [51] [52] [53] [54] [55]:

- 🌈 Solution heat treatment (SHT): The material is heated up and held at a high temperature (around 460 - 480° C) for a suitable period of time causing the dissolution of the second phases in the Al matrix to form a single-phase alloy. After that when the material is quenched rapidly to the room temperature, it results in a supersaturated solid solution.
- 🌈 Age-hardening: Then the SHT material is aged at a temperature of around 110 - 120° C for a suitable period (minimum of 24 hours). During the ageing process, finely dispersed $MgZn_2$ precipitates are formed in the matrix [56] which strengthens the material.

A typical optical micrograph of AA7075-T6 is shown in Figure 2.9 [57]. The grains are elongated (pancake shaped) in rolling direction. The microstructure could be observed to contain large amount of intermetallics (inclusions).

Figure 2.9: Optical micrograph of AA7075-T6

AA7075-T6 is precipitation strengthened due to the T6 heat treatment process. During the age-hardening, the usual sequence of the precipitations are formed according to the usual sequence followed by 7xxx Al series [58] [59] [60]:

Super saturated solid solution (SSSS) (α) phase \Rightarrow Guinier-Preston (GP) zone \Rightarrow Metastable MgZn_2 (η') phase \Rightarrow Stable MgZn_2 (η) phase.

The GP zones (Figure 2.10 (a) and (b) [61]) are coherent fine clusters of solute atoms having similar crystal structure as of the matrix.

The η' precipitation is the main strengthening factor of AA7075-T6 due to its existence in abundance and strong pinning effect on dislocations [62]. It has hexagonal crystal structure with $a = 0.496$ nm and $c = 1.40$ nm [58]. It is formed within the grains with a plate like shape [63] which can be observed from Figure 2.10 (a) and (b) [61]. η' is a metastable phase and starts to coarsen above 210°C and then transforms into stable η phase at 240°C [62].

Figure 2.10: (a) TEM micrograph of AA7050-T6: Dark field (DF) showing the variation in grain size and nanometric precipitation at the grain boundaries and within the matrix, (b) TEM micrograph of AA7050-T6: Bright field (BF) showing fine distribution of precipitates and GP zones within the Al matrix, and (c) Crystal structure of MgZn_2

η is more stable [64], much coarser and needle shaped equilibrium phase [63] which is formed along the HAGB as shown in Figure 2.10 (a) [61]. This is less coherent with Al matrix as compared to η' phase and can be observed by Electron Back-Scattered Diffraction (EBSD). This also has a hexagonal structure of MgZn_2 (Figure 2.10 (c)) belonging to $P6_3/mmc$ (194) space group with C14 structure type, hP12 Pearson sign [65] and lattice parameter of $a = 0.5221$ nm and $c = 0.8567$ nm [66]. η phase starts to dissolve in the Al matrix above a temperature of 300°C [62].

J.I. Rojas et al. [67] comprehensively studied the chemical composition, dimension, number density and volume fraction of GP zone, η' and η phases in AA7075-T6 alloy when heat treated at different temperatures between 110°C and 375°C . H.H. Kim et al. [68] analysed the effects of aging time on the precipitation hardening characteristics of rheo-forged AA7075-T6 alloy.

Several research articles have discussed about the effects of aging temperature and aging time on the precipitation evolution in cryo-rolled [69], extruded [70], sheet metal hot stamped [71] AA7075 alloy. The kinetics of precipitation evolution and phase transformation in AA7075 alloy at T6 and T651 temper conditions have been studied through Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) [72] [73] [74]. Y.H. Zhao et al. [75] also used DSC method to investigate the precipitation hardening in the ultrafine grained (UFG) AA7075 alloy processed by equal-channel angular pressing (ECAP). R. Goswami et al. [76] studied the stoichiometry of the grain boundary (GB) precipitates evolved in AA7075 at T651 and T73 tempered conditions.

AA7075-T6 material has been reported to contain two types of irregular shaped intermetallic particles or inclusions [77]. The first one is a Fe-based intermetallic which also contains Al and Cu and appears brighter than the Al matrix. This type of inclusions typically takes the form of $Al_{23}CuFe_4$, Al_2Cu_2Fe , Al_7Cu_2Fe etc [78], [79]. The second type of intermetallic contains Si and Mg as primary elements along with small amount of O and Al and appears darker than the Al matrix. Typical examples of this type of inclusions are Mg_2Si , amorphous silicon oxide [79]. These intermetallic particles can be formed during the manufacturing process. They are resistant to dissolution and play an important role in the tensile and fatigue behaviour of the material. Reports have also shown the presence of E-phase ($Al_{12}Mg_2Cr$ and $Al_{18}Mg_3Cr_2$) [79], T-phase ($Al_2Mg_2Zn_3$) [80] and S-phase (Al_2CuMg) [80] dispersoids in AA7075 alloy.

Many researchers have inferred precipitation dissolution phenomenon in different states of AA7075 alloy from the mechanical response during hot deformation [80] [81]. It has been observed that the second phase precipitates dissolve when increasing the deformation temperature and strain rate. Effects of precipitation dissolution on DRX in AA7075 is discussed in the next section.

2.3.2 Dynamic recrystallisation in AA7075 alloy

Due to the high stacking fault energy (SFE) of Al alloys, DRV and DRX may take place upon deformation at high temperatures [82]. These alloys, due to the high efficiency of DRV and low mobility of their GBs, are more prone to CDRX than to DDRX. During CDRX, the development of microstructure takes place through progressive transformation of the low angle grain boundary (LAGB) subgrains into new high angle grain boundary (HAGB) fine grains [81].

X. Yang et al. [83] studied the DRX behaviour in cold-rolled AA7075 alloy when deformed up to a strain above 40% at 525°C temperature with $2.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ strain rate (Figure 2.11). They proposed that the material undergoes CDRX by the formation of new refined grains from the subgrains originally present in the parent microstructure via grain boundary sliding (GBS) and subsequent rotation of the subgrains during the hot deformation. They also postulated that GBS takes place locally along serrated GBs and then in the grain interiors.

Figure 2.11: Inverse Pole Figure (IPF) + Grain boundary rotation maps of AA7075 samples tensile tested at 525°C with $2.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ strain rate for different strains: (a) 0, (b) 0.4, (c) 0.8 and (d) 1.6. HAGBs with misorientation more than 15° are highlighted by thick black lines. LAGBs with misorientation between 4° and 15°, and between 2° and 4° are highlighted by thin-black and red lines, respectively [83]

H.V. Atkinson et al. [84] studied the microstructure evolution in extruded AA7075-T6 alloy within its semi-solid temperature range (between 490 and 590°C). The elongated grain structure was retained when the material was heated up to a temperature below 515°C (Figure 2.12 (a) and (b)). It was attributed to the grain boundary pinning effect of the E-phase present in the microstructure. They hypothesised that when heated at higher temperatures but below 560°C, melting of ageing precipitates takes place to first form a liquid phase. When treated at sufficiently higher temperature of around 580°C, the E-phase and other dispersoids are dissolved in the liquid phase, thereby releasing the GBs so as to let them get redistributed among themselves and form a fine, equiaxed and spheroidal microstructures (Figure 2.12 (d)). The size of the spheroids increased with increasing temperature. Even though the transformation discussed here was not strain-induced, the authors referred to this behaviour as “recrystallisation” (RX).

Figure 2.12: Micrographs of AA7075-T6 samples in (a) as-extruded state, and after heated for 10 minutes in a salt bath at different temperatures: (b) 513° C, (c) 540° C and (d) 582° C and quenched in brine [84]

Z.-C. Sun et al. [80] and W. Xiao et al. [85] investigated the effects of hot deformation in extruded and rolled AA7075 alloy, respectively, within a temperature range of 300°C and 450°C for strain rates between 0.01 and 10 s⁻¹. The material seemed to undergo DRV below 350°C and DRX above 350°C. Geometrical dynamic recrystallisation (GDRX) was reported at 400°C for 0.1 and 10 s⁻¹ strain rates resulting from the serration of original pancaked grain structure. The number of fine recrystallised grains was observed to be more at higher temperature, lower strain rate and larger deformation (Figure 2.13 (b)). The average misorientation angle also increased with increasing temperature and decreasing strain rate, indicating transformation of LAGBs into HAGBs. It was inferred that the presence of second phase particles at lower temperatures and lower strain rates restricted subgrain boundary sliding. Whereas, those particles got dissolved in the matrix when the deformation temperature and strain rate were increased, which resulted in dislocation absorption and subgrain rotation leading to CDRX.

Figure 2.13: IPF image of AA7075 deformed at (a) 400° C, 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rate, 0.3 strain, (b) 400° C, 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rate, 0.5 strain, (c) 300° C, 0.1 s⁻¹ strain rate, 0.5 strain, and (d) 400° C, 1 s⁻¹ strain rate, 0.5 strain [85]

Similarly, M.R. Rokni et al. [81] studied the mechanisms behind DRX in AA7075-T6 alloy deformed within 450°C and 580°C temperatures with strain rate ranging between 0.004 and 0.4 s⁻¹. Absence of new refined grains at 450°C and 0.004 s⁻¹ strain rate indicated that the accumulated energy was not high enough to trigger DRX, and DRV was the predominant restoration process under these conditions. As the temperature and strain rates increased, new recrystallised grains were formed owing to CDRX, GDRX and even by DDRX. It is well known that large densities of finely dispersed particles and precipitates, commonly found in this type of material, restrict the dislocation movements and thereby prevent DDRX. However, the authors postulated that at 500°C, which is above the solidus temperature of around 470°C for this material [84], the precipitates are soft and easy to cut through. Consequently, at higher strain rates, greater number of dislocations are induced and get piled up at the GBs. Due to remarkable dislocation density variation across a GB, the GB starts to bulge into a new grain depicting DDRX phenomenon (Figure 2.14).

Figure 2.14: Microstructure of AA7075-T6 alloy deformed at 500° C with 0.4 s⁻¹ strain rate up to (a) strain = 0.19 and (b) strain = 0.32. The formation of new grains through bulging mechanism is depicted by arrows [81]

It could be deduced that the extent of DRX increases with decrease in the strain rate (within an order ranging between 10⁻² and 10⁰ s⁻¹) and increase in deformation temperature (within a range of 300°C and 550°C) as well as the amount of deformation. Table 2.6 summarises all the conditions in which AA7075 alloy in different states has been observed to have undergone DRX and the proposed mechanisms behind it.

State of AA7075	Temp (°C)	Strain rate (s ⁻¹)	Strain	DRV / DRX	Mechanism / Reason	Ref.
Rolled	300	0.1	0.5	DRV	Dislocation annihilation	[85]
	350 - 400	0.01 - 1	0.5	DRX	-	
Extruded	400	0.01 - 10	0.3 - 0.7	GDRX	Serration of GBs	[80]
	450			CDRX	Precipitation dissolution + dislocation absorption + subgrain rotation	
Extruded + T6	450	0.004	0.6	DRV	Restoration of dislocations	[81]
		0.04		CDRX	DRX inside grain interiors	
		0.4		CDRX + GDRX	DRX inside grain interiors + serrations in pancaked grains	
	500	0.004		CDRX + GDRX	Low dislocation density + insufficient shear stress for	
		0.04				

					dislocations to cut through precipitates	
		0.4		DDRX	Dislocation pile ups + GBs bulging	
	520	0.004 - 0.4		CDRX + DDRX + GDRX	-	
	550			DRX	-	
Cold-rolled	525	2.9×10^{-3}	> 0.4	CDRX	GBS + subgrain rotation	[83]
Extruded + T6	540 - 582	-	-	RX	Dissolution of aging precipitates + redistribution of GBs	[84]

Table 2.6: Summary of conditions and mechanisms behind DRX behaviour observed in AA7075 alloy

3 MICROSTRUCTURAL MODELLING

The deformation behaviour of a material can be predicted using constitutive models. It exists two types of material models: engineering models and physical models. The first ones are established by fitting the equations and parameters to the macroscopic experimental data (stress-strain curves) whereas physical models include underlying microstructural phenomena, such as the movement of dislocations. The aim of this project is to establish a physical model to predict the deformation behaviour of different metallic alloys in manufacturing conditions.

A material model is composed of a flow stress model, which is used to predict the evolution of the flow stress during plastic deformation. It includes a flow stress equation and a hardening rule. The flow stress model can be associated to models describing certain microstructural phenomena occurring in the material, such as recrystallisation and/or precipitation.

In this section, the flow stress model, recrystallisation model and precipitation model selected for this project are presented.

3.1 Flow stress model

Flow stress models predict the plastic deformation behaviour of a metal when it is dominated by strain hardening. However, both hardening and basic softening mechanisms, such as recovery and thermal softening, are taken into account.

A dislocation density-based model developed by L-E. Lindgren et al. [86] [87] is used in this project to model the behaviour of the materials under study. This model can describe a large range of loading conditions and it has been applied to different metallic alloys, such as AISI 316L [86], alloy 718 [31], Ti-6Al-4V [87] and AA5083 [88]. It has been proven effective in the simulation of manufacturing processes like machining, forming, welding and additive manufacturing, [5] [89] [90]. In this section, the updated version of the model is described [91].

3.1.1 Flow stress

In this model, rate-independent plasticity is assumed. This approximation dictates that plastic strain develop instantaneously so the stress state stays on the yield surface during plastic deformation. Thus, the effective applied stress is equal to the yield stress. However, internal variables of the model, which determine the yield surface, are rate dependent. Then the model uses a rate-dependent yield limit in the context of rate-independent plasticity [86].

Plastic deformation is assumed to be isotropic. It is common to split the flow stress into several parts, each one associated to an obstacle for the motion of dislocations,

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_G + \sigma^* + \sigma_{HP} + \sigma_{drag} + \sigma_p + \dots \quad (3.1.1)$$

σ_G is the athermal stress resulting from the long-range interactions of the dislocation substructure, σ^* is the friction stress required for dislocation to overcome short-range obstacles, σ_{HP} is the Hall-Petch effect contribution, σ_{drag} is the viscous drag component accounting for phonon and electron drag and σ_p is the additional stress resulting from the presence of precipitates and solutes.

For certain applications, it is possible to considered only σ_G and σ^* [87] [90] [92]. However, σ_{drag} must be taken into account for high strain rate deformation [93]. Furthermore, in the case of precipitate hardening alloys, as alloy 718 and AA7075-T6, the effect of precipitates cannot be neglected.

3.1.1.1 Long-range flow stress contribution

The long-range term is derived as [5]

$$\sigma_G = m\alpha Gb\sqrt{\rho_i}, \quad (3.1.2)$$

where m is the Taylor orientation factor translating the effect of the resolved shear stress in different slip systems into effective stress and strain quantities, α is a proportionality factor, G is the shear modulus, b is the magnitude of the burger vector and ρ_i represents the density of immobile dislocations.

The shear modulus G can be computed from the Young's modulus E and the Poisson ratio ν according to

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)}. \quad (3.1.3)$$

3.1.1.2 Short-range flow stress contribution

Thermal vibrations can assist dislocations to overcome short-range obstacles. According to the Orowan equation, the plastic strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_p$ is related to the average dislocation velocity \bar{v} via

$$\dot{\epsilon}_p = \frac{\rho_m b \bar{v}}{m}, \quad (3.1.4)$$

where ρ_m is the mobile dislocation density. The dislocation velocity \bar{v} is associated to the time taken by a dislocation to overcome an obstacle. It is considered that most of the time is spend waiting at an obstacle before being able to overcome it. Therefore, the velocity can be written as [93]

$$\bar{v} = \Lambda v_a e^{-\Delta G/kT}, \quad (3.1.5)$$

v_a being the attempt frequency, ΔG the activation energy, k the Boltzmann constant and T the temperature. The mean free path Λ corresponds to the distance covered by mobile dislocations before they are being immobilized by obstacles.

According to U.F. Kocks et al. [94], ΔG corresponds to the free energy of activation, which can be expressed as

$$\Delta G = \Delta F \left(1 - \left(\frac{\sigma^*}{\tau_0 G}\right)^p\right)^q \text{ with } 0 \leq p \leq 1 \text{ and } 0 \leq q \leq 2. \quad (3.1.6)$$

where $\Delta F = \Delta f_0 G b^3$ is the total activation energy required to overcome the lattice resistance in absence of external force. $\tau_0 G$ is the athermal shear strength, which is the shear strength that must be exceeded to move dislocations in the absence of thermal energy.

Therefore, by combining equations (3.1.4), (3.1.5) and (3.1.6), it is obtained

$$\sigma^* = \tau_0 G \left(1 - \left(\frac{kT}{\Delta f_0 G b^3} \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_p^{ref}}{\dot{\epsilon}_p}\right)\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad (3.1.7)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}_p^{ref} = \frac{\rho_m \Lambda b v_a}{m}$.

When dynamic strain aging occurs, an additional factor can be inserted in the expression of the short-range stress in order to include the effect of solute diffusion [86] [95]. The contribution of solute hardening can also be added [91].

3.1.1.3 Hall-Petch effect contribution

The contribution of the Hall-Petch effect was added to the model in order to account for dislocation pile-up at grain boundaries [91]. It can be written as

$$\sigma_{HP} = k_{HP} \frac{G}{G_{RT}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{g}}, \quad (3.1.8)$$

k_{HP} being a calibration coefficient, G represents the shear modulus at the current temperature whereas G_{RT} is the shear modulus at room temperature. g is the grain size.

3.1.1.4 Viscous drag contribution

At high strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}_p > 10^2$), the velocity of a dislocation can be limited by its interaction with phonons or electrons [93], leading to

$$v = \frac{\sigma_{drag} b}{B}, \text{ where } B = B_e + B_p \frac{T}{300}. \quad (3.1.9)$$

B_e and B_p are the electron and phonon drag coefficients respectively and v is the average dislocation velocity in this case.

Using the Orowan equation (3.1.4) with the previous equations leads to

$$\sigma_{drag} = G \left(\frac{\frac{B_e}{B_p} + \frac{T}{300}}{C_{drag}} \right) \dot{\epsilon}_p, \quad (3.1.10)$$

B_e/B_p and C_{drag} being calibration parameters.

3.1.2 Evolution of immobile dislocation density

The evolution of immobile dislocation density is composed of two parts, hardening (+) and softening (-) [5]:

$$\dot{\rho}_i = \dot{\rho}_i^{(+)} - \dot{\rho}_i^{(-)}. \quad (3.1.11)$$

The dislocation density represents the length of dislocations for a representative volume element divided by its volume. It is expressed in m^{-2} .

3.1.2.1 Hardening process

According to the Orowan equation (3.1.4), the density of mobile dislocations is proportional to the plastic strain rate and the average velocity. It was assumed that the immobile dislocation density follows the same rule [5], so its evolution can be written as

$$\dot{\rho}_i^{(+)} = \frac{m}{b\Lambda} \dot{\epsilon}_p. \quad (3.1.12)$$

The mean free Λ path can be computed from contributions of different obstacles, such as the grain and subgrain boundaries, leading to

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda} = \left(\frac{1}{g} + \frac{1}{s} + \dots \right), \quad (3.1.13)$$

where g is the grain size and s is the subgrain or sub-cell size. Effects of precipitates and solutes can be included in this equation. The grain size can be assumed to be constant and equal to the initial grain size g_0 [86] or it can be calculated using a model for grain growth [87]. The average sub-cell size can be modelled using a relation proposed by Holt [96],

$$s = \frac{K_c}{\sqrt{\rho_i}}, \quad (3.1.14)$$

where K_c is a calibration parameter. A lower limit for the subcell size can be added to this equation [86].

3.1.2.2 Softening process

Processes inducing a reduction of the dislocation density are divided into static recovery $\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(sr)}$ and dynamic recovery $\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(dr)}$ [91], leading to

$$\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)} = \dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(sr)} + \dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(dr)}. \quad (3.1.15)$$

According to L.-E. Lindgren et al. [91], the static recovery is mainly related to climb and it can be expressed as

$$\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(sr)} = c_{sr} D_v \frac{Gb^3}{kT} (\rho_i^2 - \rho_{grown}^2), \quad (3.1.16)$$

where c_{sr} is a calibration parameter, D_v is the self-diffusivity coefficient, and $\rho_{grown} = 10^{10} m^{-2}$ is the grown in dislocation density, introduced to prevent the dislocation density to become zero when hold for very long times.

Dynamic recovery is associated to the recovery by dislocation glide and it is expressed as [91]

$$\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(dr)} = \Omega \rho_i \dot{\epsilon}_p, \quad (3.1.17)$$

where, Ω is a function of temperature and strain rate. According to Bergström [97],

$$\Omega = \Omega_0 + \Omega_{r0} \left(\frac{D_{v0}}{b^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{1}{\dot{\epsilon}_p} e^{-\frac{Q}{kT}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (3.1.18)$$

Ω_0 , Ω_{r0} and D_{v0} being calibration parameters. Q corresponds to an activation energy that is calibrated for the model [91].

3.1.3 Diffusion

Diffusion occurs by the motion of point defects like vacancies and interstitial atoms, vacancy motion being the predominant diffusion mechanism. Self-diffusion corresponds to the diffusion of an atom from the crystal lattice. According to Reed-Hill and Abbaschian [98], the self-diffusion coefficient is written as:

$$D_v = D_{v0} e^{-\frac{Q_v}{kT}} = D_{v0} e^{-\frac{Q_m+Q_f}{kT}}, \quad (3.1.19)$$

where Q_v is the activation energy for self-diffusion. Q_m and Q_f are the activation energies for vacancy migration and formation, respectively. D_{v0} is a calibration parameter.

3.1.4 Stress update

To sum up, this dislocation density model is based on the following equation, describing the evolution of the immobile dislocation density:

$$\dot{\rho}_i = \left(\frac{m}{b\Lambda} - \Omega\rho_i \right) \dot{\varepsilon}_p - c_{sr} D_v \frac{Gb^3}{kT} (\rho_i^2 - \rho_{grown}^2). \quad (3.1.20)$$

Λ is defined by equations (3.1.13) and (3.1.14). Ω is defined by equation (3.1.18) and D_v is defined by equation (3.1.19).

The hardening modulus needed to update the stress is

$$H' = \frac{d\sigma_y}{d\varepsilon_p} = \frac{d\sigma_G}{d\rho_i} \frac{d\rho_i}{d\varepsilon_p} + \frac{d\sigma^*}{d\varepsilon_p} + \frac{d\sigma_{HP}}{d\varepsilon_p} + \frac{d\sigma_{drag}}{d\varepsilon_p} + \dots \quad (3.1.21)$$

σ_G is defined by equation (3.1.2), σ^* is given by equation (3.1.7), σ_{HP} is given by equation (3.1.8) and σ_{drag} is given by equation (3.1.10).

A non-exhaustive list of the model parameters is provided in Table 3.1. The model is expected to be adapted for different materials; thus, additional parameters are susceptible to be added to fit specific material behaviour. Some parameters can be assumed or known from the literature while others have to be calibrated.

Symbol	Unit	Physical meaning	Obtention	Equation
B_e		Electron drag coefficient	Calibration of $B = B_e/B_p$	(3.1.10)
B_p		Phonon drag coefficient		(3.1.10)
b	m	Magnitude of the Burger's vector	Literature	
C_{drag}		Calibration parameter in expression of σ_{drag}	Calibration	(3.1.10)

c_γ		Calibration parameter in expression of $\dot{\rho}_l^{(-)(sr)}$	Calibration	(3.1.16)
D_{v0}		Calibration parameter in the expression of D_v	Literature	(3.1.19)
G	MPa	Shear modulus	Literature	(3.1.3)
g_0	m	Initial grain size	Literature / Microscopic observation	
K_c		Calibration parameter in the expression of s	Calibration	(3.1.14)
k	J/K	Boltzmann constant	$= 1.38 \times 10^{-23}$	
k_{HP}	$N/m^{3/2}$	Hall-Petch Coefficient	Literature	(3.1.8)
m		Taylor orientation factor	Literature	
p	-	Exponent in the expression of σ^*	Calibration	(3.1.7)
q	-	Exponent in the expression of σ^*	Calibration	(3.1.7)
Q	J	Activation energy to be calibrated in expression of Ω	Calibration	(3.1.18)
Q_v	J	Activation energy for self-diffusion	Literature	(3.1.19)
α		Proportionality factor in expression of σ_G	Calibration	(3.1.2)
Δf_0		Calibration parameter in the expression of σ^* $\Delta f_0 G b^3$: activation energy required to overcome lattice resistance	Calibration	(3.1.7)
$\dot{\epsilon}_p^{ref}$	s^{-1}	Reference strain rate	Literature	(3.1.7)
Ω_0		Calibration parameter in the expression of Ω	Calibration	(3.1.18)
Ω_{r0}		Calibration parameter in the expression of Ω	Calibration	(3.1.18)
ρ_{i0}	m^{-2}	Initial dislocation density	Calibration	
ρ_{grown}	m^{-2}	grown in dislocation density in expression of $\dot{\rho}_l^{(-)(sr)}$	$= 10^{10} m^{-2}$	(3.1.16)
τ_0		Calibration parameter in the expression of σ^* $\tau_0 G$: athermal shear strength	Calibration	(3.1.7)

Table 3.1: List of parameters of the dislocation density-based model

The first version of the dislocation density-based model proposed by L.-E. Lindgren et al. [86] included the evolution of vacancy concentration as an internal state variable. The model presented here is the simplified and improved version [91].

The dislocation density-based model has the capability to connect different scales of deformation. It can account for the continuum mechanics at the macroscopic level, but also for the microstructural dynamics and dislocation dynamics at the microscopic level. Figure 14 represents the different data obtained at each scale of the model.

Figure 3.1: Data and scales in dislocation density-based model [5]

The dislocation density-based model has been adapted to a certain extent to two materials of interest in this project, Ti-6Al-4V titanium alloy and nickel-based alloy 718. The modifications made to the model in order to account for their specific behaviour are presented below.

3.1.5 Adaptation of the model to Ti-6Al-4V

B. Babu and L.-E. Lindgren [87] [5] have applied the dislocation density-based model to Ti-6Al-4V. The main modification is the inclusion of softening by globularisation. This additional softening process is added as

$$\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(glob)} = \begin{cases} \psi \dot{X}_g (\rho_i - \rho_{eq}) & \text{if } \rho_i \geq \rho_{cr} \\ 0 & \text{if } \rho_i < \rho_{cr} \end{cases} \quad (3.1.22)$$

with ρ_{cr} the critical dislocation density above which globularisation is initiated. The underlying processes for globularisation are similar to those for recrystallisation and thus it is effective only when the stored deformation energy reaches a critical value. ρ_{eq} is the equilibrium dislocation density, ψ is a calibration constant and \dot{X}_g is the globularisation rate. Calculation of X_g can be based on J.-P. Thomas and S. Semiatin [99],

$$X_g = X_d + (1 - X_d)X_s. \quad (3.1.23)$$

X_d and X_s represent respectively the dynamic and static components of the globularisation. The dynamic globularisation rate \dot{X}_d expression is also adapted from J.-P. Thomas and S. Semiatin [99]:

$$\dot{X}_d = \frac{Bk_p \varepsilon_p}{\varepsilon_p^{1-k_p} \exp(B\varepsilon_p^{k_p})}, \quad (3.1.24)$$

where B and k_p are material parameters.

Assuming that grain growth and static recrystallisation have the same driving force, the static globularisation rate \dot{X}_s can be written as [5]

$$\dot{X}_s = M \frac{\dot{g}}{g}, \quad (3.1.25)$$

M being a material parameter and g the grain size.

Furthermore, the diffusivity is different in the α and β lattice, so the formula for self-diffusivity D_v has been adapted as followed

$$D_v = D_\alpha \cdot X_\alpha + D_\beta \cdot X_\beta, \quad (3.1.26)$$

where X_α and X_β , are respectively the volume fraction of α and β phases. D_α and D_β can be expressed according to equation (3.1.19).

In addition to the parameters of Table 3.1, the model adapted to Ti-6Al-4V includes additional parameters presented in Table 3.2.

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Physical meaning</i>	<i>Obtention</i>	<i>Equation</i>
B		Material parameter in the expression of \dot{X}_d (3.1.24)	Calibration	(3.1.24)
$D_{\alpha 0}$		Calibration parameter for calculation of D_α according to (3.1.19)	Literature	(3.1.26), (3.1.19)
$D_{\beta 0}$		Calibration parameter for calculation of D_β according to (3.1.19)	Literature	(3.1.26), (3.1.19)
k_p		Material parameter in the expression of \dot{X}_d (3.1.24)	Calibration	(3.1.24)
M		Material parameter in the expression of \dot{X}_s (3.1.25)	Calibration	(3.1.25), (3.1.22)
Q_α	J	Activation energy for self-diffusion in the α phase	Literature	(3.1.26), (3.1.19)
Q_β	J	Activation energy for self-diffusion in the β phase	Literature	(3.1.26), (3.1.19)
X_α	-	Volume fraction of α phase	Literature	(3.1.26)

X_β	-	Volume fraction of β phase = $1 - X_\alpha$	Literature	(3.1.26)
ρ_{cr}	m^{-2}	Critical dislocation density above which globularisation takes place	Calibration	(3.1.22)
ρ_{eq}	m^{-2}	Equilibrium dislocation density	Calibration	(3.1.22)
ψ		Calibration parameter in the expression of $\dot{\rho}_i^{(-)(glob)}$ (3.1.22)	Calibration	(3.1.22)

Table 3.2: List of additional parameters for Ti-6Al-4V

This model has been calibrated for both low and high strain rate deformations [5], however, validation in processing conditions has only been done for the low strain rates. The project aims at providing this validation for high strain rates, as well as enhancing the modelling of the softening processes, globularisation and recrystallisation.

3.1.6 Adaptation of the model to alloy 718

The dislocation density-based model was applied to alloy 718 by M. Fisk et al. [31], by including the interaction between dislocations and precipitates. The contribution of precipitates is inserted in both the hardening part of the dislocation density evolution (equation (3.1.12)) and in the expression of the flow stress (equation (3.1.1)).

The contribution of precipitates to hardening is included in the expression of the mean free path (equation (3.1.13)), which is adapted as followed,

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda} = \left(\frac{1}{g} + \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{l_p} \right), \quad (3.1.27)$$

where l_p is the average distance between precipitates in the glide plane. For finite particles, it can be calculated according to [100]

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_s}} = \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{3f_p}} r_p, \quad (3.1.28)$$

where n_s is the number of obstacles per unit area in the glide plane, f_p is the particle volume fraction and r_p is the average particle radius. The mean free path is used to calculate the evolution of the immobile dislocation density $\dot{\rho}_i$ (equations (3.1.11) and (3.1.12)).

The contribution of precipitation to flow stress in equation (3.1.1), is expressed as

$$\sigma_p = f_s \sigma_p^{shear} + (1 - f_s) \sigma_p^{nonshear}. \quad (3.1.29)$$

f_s is the volume fraction of shearable precipitates. σ_p^{shear} and $\sigma_p^{nonshear}$ are the stresses associated to shearable and non-shearable particles respectively. They can be calculated using [101]

$$\sigma_p^{shear} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2\pi}} k_c m G \sqrt{f_p}, \quad (3.1.30)$$

$$\sigma_p^{nonshear} = \sqrt{\frac{6}{\pi}} \beta m G \frac{\sqrt{f_p}}{r_p}, \quad (3.1.31)$$

where k_c is a calibration constant and β is a parameter close to 0.5.

The critical particle radius for transition between shearable and nonshearable particles can be obtained by equating the contribution from both types of particles, equations (3.1.30) and (3.1.31). Thus, it is expressed as

$$r_c = \frac{2b\beta}{k_c}. \quad (3.1.32)$$

Then, f_s and σ_p can be determined by calculated the size distribution of the precipitates using a distribution function. r_p and f_p could be calculated by using nucleation and growth model presented in section 3.3 and 3.4.1.1.

Some of the additional parameters required when applying the dislocation density-based model on alloy 718 are presented in Table 3.3.

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Unit</i>	<i>Physical meaning</i>	<i>Obtention</i>	<i>Equation</i>
f_p	-	Particle volume fraction	Calculation using a nucleation and growth model	(3.1.28), (3.1.30), (3.1.31)
f_s	-	Volume fraction of shearable particles	Calculation using a distribution function	(3.1.29)
k_c		Calibration parameter in the expression of σ_p^{shear}	Calibration	(3.1.30), (3.1.32)
r_p	m	Average particle radius	Calculation using a nucleation and growth model	(3.1.28), (3.1.30), (3.1.31)
β		Calibration parameter in the expression of $\sigma_p^{nonshear}$	Calibration	(3.1.31), (3.1.32)

Table 3.3: List of additional parameters for alloy 718

This model has been calibrated for deformation of alloy 718 annealed and aged at low strain rate (up to 1 s^{-1}) with temperatures from 20°C to 1000°C [31]. In the current project, high strain rate tests on annealed and aged material have been performed using the Split- Hopkinson pressure bar (SHPB) for a large range of temperature (from 20°C to 1100°C) in order to calibrate the model in these conditions. The model should include nucleation and growth of precipitates. In addition, recrystallisation phenomena are also to be added to the model.

3.2 Models for dynamic recrystallisation [102]

3.2.1 Terminology of DRX

A material becomes thermodynamically unstable during the deformation process due to increase in the number of defects such as dislocations and interfaces which increases the energy stored in the system. When it is deformed at elevated temperatures, the free energy of the system is reduced by the removal of these defects through thermally activated processes. The microstructure and the properties of the material can be partially restored to their original values by recovery through annihilation and rearrangement of dislocations. Recovery processes may take place during annealing or during deformation, which are known as static recovery (SRV) and dynamic recovery (DRV), respectively.

The “formation of a new grain structure in a deformed material by the formation and migration of HAGBs driven by the stored energy” introduced by plastic deformation is termed as recrystallisation [103]. Static recrystallisation (SRX) refers to the RX process during annealing while that occurred during deformation at elevated temperatures is called DRX.

Materials having low SFE frequently undergo DDRX, where nucleation of new strain-free grains occurs, and these grains grow at the expense of regions full of dislocations. In case of materials with high SFE, subgrains with LAGBs are formed during deformation of the material which progressively transform into grains with HAGBs as the deformation increases. This is known as CDRX. There exists a third type of DRX named GDRX which is observed, for instance, on deforming aluminium to large strains at elevated temperatures. In this case, the deformed grains become elongated with local serrations and as the deformation increases, equiaxed grains with HAGBs are formed by the pinching off of serrations. It could also be noticed that if the straining is stopped after the critical strain for DDRX, but the annealing temperature does not stop sufficiently fast, the RX nuclei produced in the material will grow with no incubation time into the matrix with higher stored energy. This phenomenon is known as meta-dynamic recrystallisation (MDRX) or post-dynamic recrystallisation (PDRX).

3.2.2 Factors influencing DRX

3.2.2.1 Stacking fault energy (SFE)

In case of slip of a perfect dislocation in close-packed crystal structures, for energetic and topographic reasons, the perfect slip is favoured to dissociate into two Shockley partial dislocations. The interruption of the normal stacking sequence of atomic planes in a close-packed crystal structure is known as stacking fault. This interruption carries a certain amount of energy called as stacking fault energy (SFE). The width of the stacking fault is defined by the balance between the repulsive forces acting between the partial dislocations and attractive forces due to the surface tension of the stacking fault. This stacking fault width influences the dissociation of a perfect dislocation into partial dislocations.

During recovery, the material achieves lower energy configuration by annihilation and rearrangement of dislocations through glide, climb or cross-slip. For materials with high SFE, such as Al alloys, α -iron and titanium, the dissociation of a perfect dislocation into two partial dislocations is more difficult and hence perfect dislocation glide, climb and cross-slip can take place readily. During deformation of a high SFE material at elevated temperatures, rapid DRV takes place and the accumulation of dislocations to sustain DDRX is prevented. Instead, the LAGB subgrain structures containing limited number of dislocations are developed. The misorientation of the subgrain boundaries increase progressively with increase in strain to form HAGBs. This process is known as CDRX. If the high SFE material is deformed to a large strain with significant reduction in one direction, such as by hot rolling or hot compression, then the original grains become elongated and GDRX can take place through serrations of those elongated grains.

On the other hand, for materials with low SFE, such as silver, austenitic stainless steel etc., the stacking fault width is wider which makes climb, glide or cross-slip of the dislocation, and hence formation of subgrain structures difficult. Consequently, the dislocations get piled up at the GBs. The discrepancy in the dislocation density across the GBs leads to bulging of the grains to form new recrystallised grains indicating DDRX characteristics.

3.2.2.2 Initial grain size

The initial grain size strengthens the yield stress given by Hall-Petch relation:

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_0 + \frac{k}{\sqrt{d}}, \quad (3.2.1)$$

where, σ_0 is a material constant, k is the strengthening coefficient and d is the average grain size. Grain boundaries impede the dislocation movement. So, by

varying the grain size it is possible to modify the ease of dislocation motion and hence the yield strength of the material.

During DDRX, the GBs act as preferred nucleation sites. So, for large initial grain size, there exists fewer number of nucleation sites due to lower grain boundary area. As a result, DDRX kinetics is slower. At the same time, heterogeneities such as deformation and shear bands which are also sites for nucleation, are more readily formed in materials with larger grain sizes. The initial grain size also largely determines the shape of the stress-strain curve during DDRX. It has been reported by T. Sakai et al. [104] that if the ratio of the recrystallized and initial grain size (D_s/D_0) is larger than 2 (grain coarsening), an oscillatory stress- strain curve with multiple peaks is obtained. Lower ratio of $D_s/D_0 < 2$ (grain refining) results in a smooth curve with a single peak. The effect of initial grain size on CDRX is not as substantially studied as its DDRX counterpart.

If the material is deformed significantly in one direction, for example in rolled specimens, the grains become elongated in the rolling direction (RD). The grain thickness (H) in the normal direction (ND) is related to true strain (ϵ) and the initial grain size (D_0) by

$$H = D_0 \exp(-\epsilon). \quad (3.2.2)$$

As already discussed, in this type of processes, the microstructure tends to undergo GDRX. So lower initial grain size (D_0) will reduce the boundary thickness (H) much faster to reach the critical value for GDRX.

3.2.2.3 Thermo-mechanical processing (TMP) conditions

Most of the laboratory studies on DRX are focused on constant TMP conditions, i.e., the deformation temperature and strain rate are kept unchanged during the whole DRX processes. It is convenient to incorporate the strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) and deformation temperature (T) into a single Zener-Hollomon parameter (Z) for studying DRX, as:

$$Z = \dot{\epsilon} \exp\left(\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \quad (3.2.3)$$

where R is the gas constant and Q is an "deformation" activation energy that is often above the self-diffusion of the investigated material. The flow stress (σ) can also be related to Z through the Sellars and Tegart constitutive equation, i.e., $Z = A(\sin(\alpha\sigma))^n$ [105] where A , α and n are material constants. In general, for the DDRX regime, flow stress curves of multiple peaks appear when T is high and $\dot{\epsilon}$ is low (low Z), and single peak flow stress curves exhibit if low T and high $\dot{\epsilon}$ (high Z) (Figure 3.2 (a)). A steady state is reached for materials with these two types of

flow curves at large strains, and this steady state is dependent on Z . For CDRX and GDRX, the stress-strain curves are much less documented since the large deformation needed is usually performed by severe plastic SPD methods such as ECAP, or high-pressure torsion (HPT), which do not allow recording the stress-strain curve. Hot torsion tests can also be used to reach large deformation as long as the temperature gradient is small enough along the gauge length section.

Figure 3.2: Schematic illustration of the typically observed stress-strain curves in case of (a) DDRX, (b) CDRX and (c) GDRX

3.2.2.4 Second phase particles

Fine dispersoids tend to hinder boundary motion and slow down recrystallisation and grain growth through a Zener drag effect. By contrast, coarse constituent particles can accelerate recrystallisation by particle stimulated nucleation (PSN) due to the large amount of stored energy in the deformation zone. The solute drag effect, on the other hand, reduces the mobility of the boundary in a more complex manner, depending on grain boundary velocity. Both Zener pinning by fine particles and solute drag by alloying elements in solution slow down the grain boundary migration.

The effect of fine second-phase particles on DRX varies depending on whether they exist before the onset of recrystallisation, form during the progress of recrystallisation, or after the completion of recrystallisation. During DRX where concurrent precipitation takes place, the recrystallisation driving force and the Zener pinning force are evolving with time. According to the classical Zener pinning theory, the size and spatial distribution of the particles are assumed to be uniform which is never the case in reality. Precipitates might dissolve into solution and re-precipitate again later, such as during the weld thermal cycle during FSW where CDRX is often an important mechanism for grain refinement.

3.2.3 The Gourdet and Montheillet Model for CDRX

A simple CDRX model using the average dislocation density inside the crystallites, the average crystallite size and the distribution of LAGB misorientations as internal variables, focusing on the hot deformation of high SFE metals, is proposed by Gourdet and Montheillet [106]. The material microstructure is represented by a set of so called “crystallites” surrounded partly by LAGBs and partly by HAGBs, as schematically shown in Figure 3.3. The dislocation densities inside the crystallites, as well as the crystallite sizes are assumed to be homogeneous, which then evolves during deformation. The evolution of dislocation density inside a crystallite through strain hardening and DRV is described by the Laasraoui-Jonas equation [107]. A modification has been made to take HAGB migration into account, which also decreases the average dislocation density by replacing the swept deformed area with a dislocation free zone. A part of the recovered dislocation density contributes to formation of new LAGBs, and the other part is absorbed by the pre-existing boundaries, some of which are annihilated by HAGBs while those incorporated into LAGBs lead to the gradual misorientation increase of LAGBs into HAGBs. The predictions of the model are presented for both the transient and steady states, including stress-strain curves at various constant temperatures and strain rates, as well as the associated evolutions of microstructural quantities such as crystallite size, dislocation density and LAGB misorientation distribution. The effect of HAGB migration on these parameters is emphasized.

Figure 3.3: Schematic representation of the CDRX microstructure illustrating the internal variables of the model: the mean intercept length D , the dislocation density inside the subgrains ρ_i , and the misorientation angles of the LAGBs. (thick lines: HAGBs, fine lines: LAGBs)

This model links the stress-strain curve to key microstructural parameters and is capable to predict the evolution of crystallite size, dislocation density and misorientation distribution with strain, under different constant hot deformation conditions. However, crystallographic texture effects were neglected, and the fact that LAGB is able to migrate, as demonstrated when the stress or strain rate changes during deformation, was neglected in this model.

3.3 Classical nucleation and growth model

The Classical Nucleation and Growth Theory (CNGT) [108] [109] [110] [111] [112] consists of two parts; one for nucleation and the other for change in size of the new phase. The theory with various extensions is applied to vaporization, solidification and many solid-state phase changes. All phase changes have in common that Gibbs energy of the new phase composition is lower than the current one and therefore plays a pivotal role in the model both for nucleation as well as growth/shrinkage of a phase. Gibbs energy is here extended with contributions from surface energy as well as elastic misfit energy between the phases. This energy drives the phase change and when it reaches a minimum, equilibrium state is obtained. Thus, a new phase may develop if the energy decreases. Gibbs free energy for forming a spherical embryo of radius r can be written as:

$$G(r) = G_{chem} + G_{el} + G_{srf} = g_{chem} \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 + w_{el} (\chi) \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 + \gamma_{srf} 4\pi r^2, \quad (3.3.1)$$

where g_{chem} is the chemical energy per unit volume giving current driving force, w_{el} is elastic misfit energy per unit volume, γ_{srf} is the free energy per unit surface area. The surface (G_{srf}) and elastic (G_{el}) energies oppose the new phase even if the chemical driving force is negative.

Thermal fluctuations may create a nucleus that is sufficiently large to overcome this energy barrier and start to grow. The critical nucleus size (r_{cr}) can be obtained by setting the derivative of equation (3.3.1) to 0 and then solving for r_{cr} :

$$\left. \frac{\partial G}{\partial r} \right|_{r_{cr}} = (g_{chem} + w_{el}) 4\pi r_{cr}^2 + \gamma_{srf} 8\pi r_{cr} = 0 \Rightarrow r_{cr} = -\frac{2\gamma_{srf}}{(g_{chem} + w_{el})}. \quad (3.3.2)$$

The corresponding peak of the energy barrier is given by:

$$G_{cr} = \frac{16\pi}{3} \frac{\gamma_{srf}^3}{(g_{chem} + w_{el})^2}. \quad (3.3.3)$$

The Becker-Döring [113] nucleation theory gives the nucleation rate of these nuclei. It depends on the jump of solutes to the nuclei and therefore also includes diffusivity. The nucleation rate in is written as:

$$\dot{N}_{BD}^{ss} = Z \frac{A_f r_{cr}^2 D_l^{a_{srf}} X_a^\alpha Z}{a V_{cell}} N_s e^{-G_{cr}/k_B T}, \quad (3.3.4)$$

where Z is the Zeldovich factor, a is the lattice size, and D_i^a is the lattice diffusivity of the solute required to jump into the growing phase in order to attain the critical size and then grow, X_a^{sf} is the concentration of solute in the parent phase at the interface of the new phase, N_s is the total number of available nucleation sites, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and T is the temperature.

Further assumptions are required for formulating an equation for the growth/shrinkage of the new phase. It is often assumed that diffusion is the rate controlling step and often this is simplified to focus on the slowest diffused solute. The solute concentration may look like in Figure 3.4.

Two basic approaches exist in this case. The fastest is to compute the evolution of mean size of the precipitates and their volume fraction. This is based on the assumption of a size distribution called the LSW-distribution following Lifschitz and Slyosov [114] and Wagner [115]. The other option is to discretise the size into classes and trace the evolution of the number of precipitates in each one of them. The growth equation is then expressed in a format as:

$$\dot{r} = \frac{\alpha_c}{r} \left(\frac{1}{r_{v0}} - \frac{1}{r} \right) = \frac{\alpha_c}{r_{v0} r^2} (r - r_{v0}), \quad (3.3.5)$$

where

$$\alpha_c = \frac{D_a^{l\ eq} C_a^\alpha 2l_c}{\infty \Delta_a^\beta} \quad (3.3.6)$$

and

$$r_{v0} = \frac{eq C_a^\alpha 2l_c}{\infty \Delta_a^\alpha}. \quad (3.3.7)$$

Furthermore, the differences in concentrations are needed which are:

$$\infty \Delta_a^\alpha = {}^m C_a^\alpha - {}^{eq} C_a^\alpha \quad (3.3.8)$$

and

$$\infty \Delta_a^\beta = {}^{eq} C_a^\beta - {}^{eq} C_a^\alpha. \quad (3.3.9)$$

The concentrations are shown in Figure 3.4. The capillarity length is given by:

$$l_c = \frac{\gamma_{sf} V_m^\beta}{R_G T}, \quad (3.3.10)$$

with the molar volume of the new phase is V_m^β and R_G is the gas constant.

Figure 3.4: Atomic fraction of 'a' atoms versus distance ρ from centre of precipitate. It is indicated that the equilibrium composition depends on temperature and size of precipitate. The atomic fractions can be replaced by volume concentrations etc.

3.4 Models for precipitation evolution

Precipitation modelling ideally distinguishes between three successive phases; nucleation, growth and coalescence. In the initial stage, the number of precipitations increases which is called nucleation. During growth, there are no more new precipitates created and their number remains constant; only their size increases. At last, the larger precipitates grow at the expense of the smaller ones and thus the number of precipitations decreases which is called the coalescence stage. This breakdown is mostly conceptual, and in reality, these stages overlap while the transition of one regime to another is still going on.

3.4.1 Modelling for nickel-based superalloys

During the thermo-mechanical process of nickel-based alloys, nucleation of precipitates occurs. The precipitation kinetics will be modelled using the classical model with an initial stage of nucleation and growth followed by a stage of growth and coarsening. The modelling of this phenomena will be based on the modelling proposed by A. Deschamps et al. [116] for the transition from nucleation-growth to growth-coarsening stage.

3.4.1.1 Nucleation and growth

The nucleation rate is obtained by:

$$\left. \frac{dN}{dt} \right|_{nucl} = (N_{tot} - N) Z \beta^* \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G^*}{kT}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\tau}{t}\right) \quad (3.4.1)$$

with

$$N_{tot} = 0.5\rho^{1.5} \quad (3.4.2)$$

and

$$\beta^* = \frac{4\pi R_c^2 DC}{a_0^4} \quad (3.4.3)$$

where N_{tot} is the total number of nucleation sites (i.e. dislocation nodes), τ is the incubation time for nucleation, which is taken to be zero considering that heterogeneous nucleation in the present system is almost an instantaneous process requiring no incubation time, ΔG^* is the activation energy for nucleation, k is the Boltzmann constant, Z is the Zeldovich factor which is approximately 1/20, β^* is the atomic impingement rate, a_0 is the lattice parameter of austenite and C and D are the bulk concentration and diffusivity of the major microalloying element, respectively. The critical energy barrier can be calculated numerically from the free energy balance between the chemical free energy, the interfacial free energy and the elastic energy of the dislocation. The formulation used by H.S. Zurob [117] is given below as:

$$\Delta G = V\Delta G_V + A\gamma - \left(\frac{\mu b^2 r \ln\left(\frac{r}{b}\right)}{2\pi(1-\nu)} + \mu b^2 r/5 \right) \quad (3.4.4)$$

where V is the volume of the transformed nucleus, ΔG_V is the chemical free energy difference per unit volume of the transformation, μ is the shear modulus, b is the Burger's vector, ν is the Poisson's ratio, A and γ are the surface area and surface energy of the nucleus, respectively.

At the nucleation and growth stage, the instantaneous number density of nuclei can now be obtained from the integration of the nucleation rate $\frac{dN}{dt}$. The growth of the nuclei is controlled by the diffusion of microalloying element M . The growth rate is given as [117] [118]:

$$\left. \frac{dr}{dt} \right|_{growth} = \frac{D_{eff}}{r} \frac{C_M - C_M^r}{C_M^p - C_M^{Eq}} + \frac{1}{n} \frac{dn}{dt} (\alpha r^* - r) \quad (3.4.5)$$

$$D_{eff} = D_{pipe} \pi R_{core}^2 \rho + D_{bulk} (1 - \pi R_{core}^2 \rho) \quad (3.4.6)$$

where D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient which is a combination of pipe diffusion and bulk diffusion. The dislocation networks provide fast diffusion paths for the solute to transport and thus D_{eff} depends on the dislocation density ρ , and πR_{core}^2 which is the cross-section area of the dislocation core. C_M^r , C_M^p and C_M^{Eq} denote the concentration of M in equilibrium with a precipitate particle of radius r , the concentration of M in the precipitate and the concentration of M in equilibrium with a large (infinite) precipitate, respectively. The first term in equation (3.4.5) is the standard diffusion controlled growth law

for a spherical particle [119] and the second term is the rate of change of the average particle radius as a result of the nucleation of dn new particles of size αr^* during a time increment dt [117] [116]. α is taken as 1.05 in the model.

3.4.1.2 Growth and coarsening

The growth rate in equation (3.4.5) is driven by the supersaturation of solute in the matrix. In the coarsening stage, the average precipitate size will increase as a result of the size-driven competition between individual precipitates. Following A. Deschamps et al. [116], the rate of change of particle size during coarsening was given as [120]:

$$\left. \frac{dr}{dt} \right|_{coarsening} = \frac{D_{eff} C_M^r - C_M^{27r/23}}{r (C_M^P - C_M^{Eq})} \quad (3.4.7)$$

$$\left. \frac{dN}{dt} \right|_{coarsening} = \left. \frac{dr}{dt} \right|_{coarsening} \cdot \left[\frac{r^* C_M}{r (C_M^P - C_M)} \left(\frac{3}{4\pi r^3} - 2N + \frac{4\pi r^3 N^2}{3} \right) - 3N \right] \quad (3.4.8)$$

Under conditions of simultaneous growth and coarsening, the average rate of changes of particle size and number density of nuclei are given as:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = (1 - f_{coarse}) \left. \frac{dr}{dt} \right|_{growth} + f_{coarse} \left. \frac{dr}{dt} \right|_{coarsening} \quad (3.4.9)$$

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = f_{coarse} \left. \frac{dN}{dt} \right|_{coarsening} \quad \left(\left. \frac{dN}{dt} \right|_{growth} = 0 \right) \quad (3.4.10)$$

$$f_{coarse} = 1 - erf \left(4 \left(\frac{r}{r_n} - 1 \right) \right) \quad (3.4.11)$$

It is planned to measure the average precipitate size and the number density.

3.4.2 Modelling for Aluminium and its alloys

The Myhr and Grong model [121] builds on the previous work of R. Kampmann et al. [122] which aims to determine the evolution of the size distribution of precipitates. These precipitates interact through a solid solution whose concentration is assumed to be spatially uniform (mean field hypothesis). This model differs from the single-radius model, which only calculates the evolution of the moments of order 1 (mean radius) and 3 (volume fraction) of this distribution. The precipitates are assumed to be spherical, and the evolution as a function of time of the radius distribution is governed by the partial differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial J}{\partial r} + S \quad (3.4.12)$$

where n is the radius distribution of the precipitates per unit volume, i.e. $n(r,t) dr$ is the number of precipitates per unit volume having a radius between r and $r + dr$ at time t , J is the flux of precipitates, i.e. $J(r, t) dt$ the algebraic number of precipitates per unit volume exceeding the radius r between time t and $t + dt$, S is a source term (germination of new precipitates), either $S(r, t) dr dt$ is the algebraic number of precipitates per unit volume which appear between the time t and $t + dt$, and having a radius of between r and $r + dr$.

The precipitate flow J can be related to the size distribution n using the velocity of precipitation growth v :

$$J = nv \quad (3.4.13)$$

The mean radius and the volume fraction of the precipitates are given by the following expressions:

$$r_m(t) = \int_0^{\infty} r \frac{n(r,t)}{\int_0^{\infty} n(r,t) dr} dr \quad (3.4.14)$$

And

$$f_v(t) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 n(r,t) dr \quad (3.4.15)$$

To solve this partial differential equation, the Myhr and Grong model [121] uses the size distribution of the discretized precipitates, in size class r containing a number per unit volume $N_i(r)$ of precipitates of radius $r_i = i\Delta r$.

In the Figure 3.5 [123], each class defines a control volume, and the phenomena of initiation, growth and dissolution result in particle flows between classes. Finally, the density of precipitates at time $t + \Delta t$ is written as:

$$N_i(t + \Delta t)\Delta r = N_i(t)\Delta r - (Nv)_{i+1/2}\Delta t + (Nv)_{i-1/2}\Delta t + s_i\Delta t \quad (3.4.16)$$

with

$$(Nv)_{i-1/2} = \begin{cases} N_{i-1}(t) v_{i-1/2} & \text{si } v_{i-1/2} > 0 \\ N_{i-1}(t) v_{i-1/2} & \text{si } v_{i-1/2} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.4.17)$$

$$(Nv)_{i+1/2} = \begin{cases} N_{i-1}(t) v_{i+1/2} & \text{si } v_{i+1/2} > 0 \\ N_{i+1}(t) v_{i+1/2} & \text{si } v_{i+1/2} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3.4.18)$$

Figure 3.5: Calculation of the evolution of the size distribution of precipitates after an increment of time t

Figure 3.6: Flow chart of the program calculating the evolution of the size distribution of precipitates as a function of time [121]

The flowchart (Figure 3.6) shows the main steps of the program written by Myhr and Grong to calculate the evolution of the size distribution. In finite differences, the expressions for the mean radius and the volume fraction are:

$$r_m = \frac{\sum_i N_i r_i}{\sum_i N_i} \quad (3.4.19)$$

and

$$f_v = \sum_i \frac{4}{3} \pi N_i \Delta r r_i^3 \quad (3.4.20)$$

The time step Δt in the algorithm is chosen so that the precipitates cannot skip a class, so that the class with the highest growth rate only grows that of $\frac{\Delta r}{2}$. In practice, it is reached by the smallest class in the distribution that is dissolving. This method of resolution has the disadvantage of to have a time step limited by the dissolution of the precipitates, and therefore to consume a lot of computational time to describe the dissolution of small precipitates, which isn't necessarily the most interesting part of the cast. To compensate for this, otherwise, we choose a solution proposed by D. Gendt [124] which is to arbitrarily remove all precipitates whose radii will be less than $\frac{r^*}{10}$. This trick of numerical calculation does not degrade the accuracy on the interesting parts of the distribution and greatly speeds up the calculation. For the upper bound of the distribution, the first empty class will only be incremented if the particle flow is higher than a minimum value to avoid too many particles widespread distribution.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- The microstructural characteristics of the selected alloys were investigated. The physical mechanisms incorporated in the existing microstructural models were discussed.
- The simulation settings, that have been used for modelling different microstructural phenomena, were enlisted. The value of the parameters could be obtained from the literature, flow stress behaviour, microstructural analysis and model calibration.
- Several mechanical tests have been performed on the selected materials at different loading conditions using SHPB setup and Gleeble thermo-mechanical simulator. The mechanical results could be used by other ESRs to calibrate their models.
- Microstructural characterisation of the deformed specimens are being carried out using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The analysis of the microstructure could also be used as inputs in the models being developed by ESRs in WP2.

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